

STATE EXPERIENCE OF BREWING OF THE ELITE WHEELING FARM

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Forming scientific conclusions based on a comparative study of the seed production system of agricultural crops in a number of countries of the world, with a deep study of the current situation in our country, becomes relevant in the context of globalization. Research shows that the seed production system in developed countries is developing on the basis of the following forms and relationships. Development experiences of seed farms of several developed countries were studied and conclusions and proposals were developed for implementation in our country.

Ispoil agriculture is the most developed branch of the national economy: Ispoil country has a geographically unfavorable climate for farming, most of its territory is desert, and there is a shortage of water. In addition, Israel has become a world leader in the export and production of agricultural products.

natural arable land is used for agriculture. Today, agricultural production is 2.5% of GDP and 3.6% of GDP. Israel imports only 3.7 percent of grain, oil, meat, coffee, cocoa, and sugar, and does not produce 95 percent of its own needs.

In Ispoil, there are several companies specializing in the production of agricultural crops. The research and improvement work in the field of soybean breeding in Israel is carried out under the supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture.

Seeds Technologies - Founded in 1996, the company has extensive experience and knowledge in breeding, processing, and specialized in the development and improvement of vegetable seeds. It has equipment for processing and storage of wood, as well as a modern laboratory. The company has many representative offices and sells its products in more than 30 countries. It mainly produces the upuglap for expopt.

Top seeds International Ltd is an innovative and high quality dupagaylap production company. The goal of the company is to guarantee the taste of vegetables and fruits and the high productivity of plants, due to the development of genetically resistant varieties of plants. The company closely cooperates with more than 100 countries of the world. The company is engaged in the cultivation of tomatoes, root crops, peppers, bodping, patisson, tapvuz, bpokkoli, onions, melons

and pumpkins. The company has 120 full-time employees and annual turnover of 7.82 mln. the locker has working capital.

Hazera Berurim is a world leader in the field of breeding. The company combines many years of experience with modern technology, develops and sells a wide variety of vegetable crops and seeds around the world. Hazera Berurim has a wide distribution network located in Israel and the Netherlands, with branches in 12 countries and services in over 100 countries.

Zeraim Gedera is part of the Global Syngenta Group, one of the world's leading agricultural technology companies. Zeraim Gedera was founded in 1952 and is considered a leader in the agricultural sector of Israel with the production of high quality wheat. The company mainly produces kalampip, pomidop, bodping, pumpkin, tapvuz and melon upuglap. The company's goal is to provide high-quality products and services to customers and customers, as well as providing professional advice and mentorship.

Germany took the 3rd place in the European Union for the cultivation of agricultural crops and became the world's largest producer of cotton.

Hepmania Food and Agriculture Ministry's policy in the field of agriculture . The Ministry of Food and Agriculture carries out the task of establishing the legal framework for the agricultural sector to the main agency of the Ministry - the Fedepal Agency for Agriculture and Food and its subordinate Fedepal plant classification agency.

The 2020 to 2035 agricultural strategy was adopted by the Hungarian Parliament and includes six main goals. In order to achieve this goal, 12 activities have been defined by the Ministry, including selection of agricultural crops.

The platform was developed in partnership with more than 40 organizations, civil society and industry stakeholders.

The general objectives of this strategy are as follows:

- provision of food, feed and bio-raw materials;
- to provide support for fepmeplap;
- to strengthen protection of environment and pesupslap;
- preservation of biodiversity in agriculture;
- increasing the contribution of agriculture to climate protection and adaptation of agriculture to climate change;
- To increase the general acceptance of cheating in the hepmania community.

The structure and the main organization of the Hepmania breeding sectop.

Its main organization is:

- Fedepal support for agriculture and food;

- Fedepal plant variety application;
- Private sector:
 - Association of Hepmania plant breeding companies;
 - Hepmania Upuglapi Union;
 - Hepmania agrobusiness association;
 - Society for supporting innovation in business organization;
 - Research Institute:
 - Federal scientific-research institute of agriculture named after Yuliy Kyun;
 - Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Plant Research (manages the gene bank in Gatepsleben, one of the world's largest gene banks for crops);
 - Max Planck Research Institute of Plant Breeding;
 - Plant Selection Society.

Fedepal Agriculture and Food Development is an organization that develops the general policy of agriculture in Hepmania. Mazkup has developed the following measures to increase the yield of wheat:

1. Disease resistance
2. Adaptation to the climatic conditions
3. Adapting to the tu ply tupklap
4. Brewing certain qualities and characteristics of a traditional tuplap or variety
5. Increase in productivity
6. Quality (size, storage capacity, taste) increase
7. Brewing of upug'lap for its eptapishap variety, cold resistance and other characteristics.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) Biodiversity Information and Coordination Plan coordinates the conservation and utilization of the genetic diversity of the plant population.

The Information and Coordination Center manages the national inventory of plant genetic resources in Hepmania. Information about the existing gene bank in Germany and related institutions, the genetic database will be published openly.

Fedepal is tasked with providing support to private breeding companies, ensuring that small-scale farmers receive quality breeding material, developing a certified breeding system for long-term innovation in the field of breeding, and improving the legal framework.

For example, in Hepmania, the patent right applies only to the technological aspect of the breeding stock. If the company has developed a new agricultural crop variety and applied for inclusion of this variety in the National Register, the quality, yield, resistance to pests and diseases, differentiation from other varieties, variety and

maturity of the new variety should be tested in an open field or in a greenhouse for 2-3 years. bran

Approximately 20% of the 900 agricultural varieties submitted for national registration each year will be registered by the variety committee using the Fedepal Osimliklap variety and will be included in the National Register.

Fedepal supports plant variety protection on behalf of Germany in the European Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV), as a member of the Governing Council of the Community Plant Varieties Organization (SPVO) of the European Union, and as a member of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). has the authority to adopt a long-term and systematic approach to the internationally agreed method of certification of success.

The private sector includes many large and small private companies, and invests 15% of the company's profits in research and development.

Currently, about 60 private farms engaged in the cultivation and sale of about 130 varieties of agricultural crops have their own selection process and are developing more than 300 varieties of wheat.

Breeding has a 30-50 percent share in the increase of the yield of agricultural crops, and last year this share exceeded 80 percent, and the annual turnover of grain production in Hepmania is 26 billion euros, and the annual increase in grain yield largely depends on selection.

The Ministry of Food and Agriculture finances and has political influence over many scientific research institutions involved in the selection of agricultural crops. The state sector provides funding for scientific research institutes, focusing on long-term basic research and developing new types of research:

1. Long-term fundamental research aimed at ensuring the availability of adapted navlap in the long-term perspective;
2. Brewing traditional breeding methods using wild crops such as apples and vines;
3. Funding 25 years of research before a new variety is released.

The Food and Agriculture Organization's mission to fund research to determine the complete genome of Germany's most important crop will fuel innovative research and enable rapid and targeted breeding of new cultivars.

Also, the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, in cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Research, is funding a large-scale project in the field of agricultural research.

For example, the research project "Plant Biotechnology of the Future", which includes a brief analysis of 28 Hepmania subspecies, is funded mainly by the Education and Research Service of 9 different institutions.

Chinese government has gradually closed the system of subsidizing grain, rice, and corn farmers to subsidize the purchase of grain. The goal of China's agricultural subsidy policy is to increase the country's production of grain, rice, and corn, ensure food security, and increase the country's income.

According to the document published by the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Agriculture, Bank of China, and the Sugupta Regulatory Commission, many enterprises, agricultural cooperatives, and farming companies are subsidized by the Chinese government. A substantial subsidy covers losses that may occur as a result of natural disasters, plant diseases and droughts, and other hazards.

In the Republic of Misapab, the quality level of cotton has been increased due to the fact that it was taken by the state (Cotton Association and Cotton Control Organization) during the strict cultivation of cotton.

According to the state standard, there should be 1-2 foreign varieties in 1000 plants, that is, 99.8-99.9% variety is required. In order to do this, the country of Misp is geographically divided into 3 regions (north, south and south) and specific cotton varieties are assigned to each region. If it is determined that another variety is planted in this area, the plant in the field will be burned, and the damage will be compensated at the expense of FEPMEP, and the state will compensate the profit expected to be received by the FEPMEP farm. It is worth noting that in Misp, the success of one cotton variety is established in one plant.

In the US, breeding is mainly done by private breeding companies and specialized breeding firms. Due to the strong competition in the field, it is recommended to grow high-quality hemp only in regions with very favorable soil and climatic conditions, and a long growing season. As a result, a variety of 99% and 90% germination is produced.

In Possia, the policy of cultivation of grain and pulses is carried out by the Ministry of Agriculture and its responsibility in the regional government. Bipoq, Ulap only designates the area of cultivation of elite and peppoduction in its territory. Upugliklap is grown and bred by local yarn companies and private cooperatives and upuglik farms. The company or cooperative guarantees the quality and variety of the product it produces. Ozapo ensures the strength of the competition and the high quality of the product. The quality of the pump is 98-99 percent in the supep elite and elite pump, and 95-96 percent in the peppoduction pump.

Canada, the corn breeding system is managed by the Breeding Association. The association coordinates the selection and breeding activities of the country, sets requirements on the quality of varieties and varieties, ensures the reproduction of

new varieties and determines the volume of production of varieties. The government will set the cap on the production and sale of the product.

Italian state, farming is mainly done by two cooperative organizations in close contact with Fedepal agponomy. Ulap manufactures sorghum on the basis of a contract with the femmep farm and supplies it for conditioning (mapomi) at its own sorghum treatment plant.

Swedish state, a joint-stock company is engaged in the production and sale of agricultural crops. The largest of the group is the joint-stock company "Swedish Breeding Institute", which owns a breeding institute, a station and a wool breeding farm.

In Bel opus Pespublika, the breeding system is supported by 2 Research and development projects, which include 21 entities operating under the Belsemena farm and its regional farm. In the republic, high-generation horticultural crops are cultivated in 610 elite farms and pepoduction horticultural crops are grown in special farms. In order to increase the quality of sorghum, 40 sorghum plants will be cleaned, treated, doped and packed in the next year.

According to the information given above, in many countries, the development of different and organizational work in the rice farming system, the strength of quality and competition, the cleaning, threshing, dressing and packaging of rice in a separate factory ensure the production of high quality rice of the agricultural crop. Based on the experience of the studied foreign countries, the following conclusions and proposals were developed:

creation of exportable, productive, high-quality, disease-resistant selective varieties and F1 hybrids of vegetable, sugar, leguminous, oilseed and food crops in scientific and research institutes, as well as organization of primary seed production;

Training of specialists in foreign countries (at least 1 year) and exchange of experience in order to learn modern methods of creating F1 hybrids;

- In order to develop breeding and seed production in scientific research institutes, the establishment of laboratories with 5-6 staff members financed from the state budget.

- to create a specialized cluster in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its regions, attracting foreign investors, to form a mechanism for the purchase, accumulation, processing and delivery of vegetable, pulse, leguminous, oil and fodder seeds, and providing incentives for the purpose of state support.

- introduction of a system of subsidies by the state to the entities that grow vegetables, sugarcane, legumes, oilseeds and food seeds.

- To strengthen the material and technical base of the elite seed farms and organizations in the central system, to cancel the payment of dividends (dividends) to the state budget from the net profit at the end of the year for the purpose of their financial support;

- the transfer of elite seed farms to the private sector will lead to the deterioration of the fertility of varieties in the future and, most importantly, to a sharp increase in high (elite) generation seeds in large areas, and as a result, to an increase in the price of seeds.

Also, the life of a variety created after many years of effort by the breeders will be short, that is, the work of family separation, field observations, selection based on individual selection and laboratory analysis will not be fully completed, and in view of the decrease in fertility, elite seed farms will be sold completely through public auctions. deregistration of enterprises.

- in order to prevent the entry of untested seeds of agricultural crops into the domestic market, it is necessary to introduce the system of importation of varieties and hybrids included in the State Register and to amend the Law "On Seed Production".

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